

Performance comparison of GWO-based Fractional Order PID controller and Sliding Mode controller

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Abstract: Enhancing frequency stability of micro grid linked power systems is the goal of this work, which presents the GWO-FO-PID controller and the SMC as load frequency controllers (LFC). The GWO algorithm minimises the objective function to optimise the FO-PID controller's settings in the GWO-FO-PID controller. Solving for the integral square error (ISE) of frequency deviations is the formulation of the objective function. The Sliding Mode Controller (SMC) uses the sliding surface principle to determine the settings. In the face of load disruptions, variations in wind and solar power, and linked micro grid systems covering one or two areas, the suggested controllers were developed and put into action.

Keywords: Integration Square Error (ISE), Sliding Mode Controller (SMC), and Fractional Order based on GWO (GWO-FO-PID).

Introduction

The electric power system consists of a network of power plants and load centres spread out across a large area. Due to globalisation, there has been an increase in both industrial demand and per capita energy consumption [1]. In response to climate change concerns, governments worldwide have launched programmes to incorporate renewable energy sources into the electrical system. However, only a small number of these efforts have received funding from affluent countries. System prices have dropped even lower per unit thanks to the meteoric rise of renewable energy. This allows for the fast incorporation of renewable energy sources but also reducing the system's flexibility

due to its stochastic character. Even though renewable energy may be effectively integrated into demand centres, linking these centres to power plants has proven to be somewhat challenging. A difficult aspect of controlling the flow of energy from supply to demand is load frequency management.

Power and frequency fluctuations could be better managed with the use of automatic generation control (AGC). As time went on, integral, proportional, and PID controllers became the de facto standards for managing load frequency. The device's functionality is significantly impacted by the controller's configuration. In order to deal with LFC, several other methods have been used. Linear quadratic [6], decentralisation [5], and resilient control [2-4] are only a few of the numerous characteristics of the LFC system. Making these concepts a reality is tough because of all the limits they have. In 2016, Shankar and Mukherjee [7] studied LFC learning with expanded power sources in single-area power systems, enlarged power sources in connected two-area power systems, and both types of power sources in single-area power schemes. Tuning the gain of the classical controller effectively determines the efficacy of remembering and jumping. A frequency management framework was proposed in 2019 by Zhang et al. [8] and the American Grid Corporation (AGC) for transmission networks with several control zones and load-side controllers to govern tie-line powers and system frequency, among other things. boundaries that govern the process. In 2018, Aziz et al. [9-10] assessed the LFC of a fusion power system with

unanticipated wind turbines integrated with hydroelectric, thermal, and gas-based power plants. The type-3 wind plant idea now includes a moving average filter and a frequency-active power controller that is reliant on the dynamic dead band. The suggested controllers mitigate the drawbacks of the current controllers. To make linked micro grid systems more stable, this research suggests using GWO-FO-PID controllers and SMC controllers.

1. System under study

The micro-grid power system that is being considered is shown in Fig. 1. A thermal energy generator that is driven by wind and sun and connected to a loading hub (Area-1) is shown in Figures 1 and 2 [5]. The Area-1 frequency

1.2 Design of micro grid

Microgrids are constructed using a single thermal power unit and sign of GWQ-FO-PID controller

Grey Wolf Optimizer based Fractional Order PID (GWO-FO-PID) controller is shown in fig.2. The

fluctuates greatly due to the intermittent nature of renewable energy sources. It is possible that PI or PID controllers will not be able to solve this issue. The purpose of the area frequency controller is to maintain system stability when various disturbances occur for the purposes of this study.

1.1 Objective Function

The objective function is formulated as a combination on Integral Square Errors (ISEs) of three areas:

$$Objective\ Function\ (OB) = ISE_1 + ISE_2 + ISE_3 \tag{1}$$

renewable energy sources such as wind turbines and solar systems. All of the following sources are included in the transfer function model [5].

parameters of FO-PID (K_p, K_i, K_d, λ and μ) controller are optimized using GWO algorithm and is shown in fig.3.

Fig.2. GWO based fractional order PID controller design.

Fig.3 Structure of Sliding Mode Controller

Fig.3 GWO algorithm for optimal parameters calculation of fractional order PID controller

$$C = [1 \quad 0 \quad 0]$$

Transforming the system represented in eq-5 using the transformation matrix T_c such that the new state vector is $\zeta = T_c x$

Where

$$T_c = [C \quad CA \quad CA^2]$$

$$\zeta = [\zeta_1 \quad \zeta_2 \quad \zeta_3]^T$$

$$\zeta_1 = \Delta f_i$$

$$\zeta_2 = -0.05 \Delta f_i + 6 \Delta P_{gi}$$

$$\zeta_3 = 0.0025 \Delta f_i - 21.1326 \Delta P_{gi} + 20.832 \Delta X_{gi}$$

To address the uncertainties including variations in wind and solar energy generation, sliding surface is designed.

$$\rho = k_1 \zeta_1 + k_2 \zeta_2 + k_3 \zeta_3$$

Where k_1, k_2, k_3 are selected such that the roots lie on the half s-plane. A control input is designed to stabilize the system operating frequency.

$$u = 0.003(124.71E_1 - 46.03E_2 - 16.54E_3) + 0.003\{k_3^{-1}[k_1E_2 + k_2E_3\gamma \text{sign}\rho]\}$$

2. Simulation results

The proposed controllers are designed and implemented in MATLAB/Simulink and tested on single area interconnected micro grid system and three area micro grid system under load disturbances, wind and solar power fluctuations.

Case 1: single area interconnected micro grid system with load disturbances, wind and solar

power fluctuations

The simulation diagram of single area system with load disturbances, wind & solar power fluctuations is shown in fig.5. Simulations results with load disturbance initiated at 4 seconds with 0.01p.u in area 1 and wind & solar power fluctuations in area 1 are shown in fig.6. The performance parameters are listed in table.1. From the table it is clear that GWO-FO-PID controller performance is better than the SMC controller.

Fig.5 Simulation diagram of a single-area system with load disturbance, wind and solar power fluctuations

Fig.6 Single area time response of Δf_1

Table.1 performance parameters of single area

Performance parameter	Type of controller	Rise Time	Settling Time	Peak	Peak Time
Af_1	SMC	0.0083	46.4606	0.172	4.59
	GWO-FO-PID	0.0460	45.9168	0.055	4.15

Case-2: two area interconnected micro grid system with load disturbances and solar power fluctuations

The simulation diagram of two area system with load disturbances & solar power fluctuations is shown in fig.7. Simulations results with load disturbance initiated at 5 seconds with 0.01p.u in area

1 and solar power fluctuations in area 1 are shown in fig.8-13. The performance parameters are listed in table.2. From the table it is clear that GWO-FO-PID controller performance is better than the SMC controller.

Fig.7 Simulation diagram of two-area system with load disturbance and solar power fluctuations

Fig.8 Time response of Δf_1 with load disturbance and solar power fluctuations in area 1.

Fig.9 Time response of Δf_2 with load disturbance and solar power fluctuations in area 1.

Fig.10 Time response of ΔP_{g1} with load disturbance and solar power fluctuations in area 1.

Fig.12 Time response of ΔP_{T1} with load disturbance and solar power fluctuations in area 1.

Fig.13 Time response of ΔP_{T2}

Table.2 performance parameters of two area

Performance parameters	Type of controller	Settling Time	Peak	Peak Time
Af ₁	SMC	6.9205	0.1727	5.6060
	GWO-FO-PID	6.0080	0.0595	5.1690
Af ₂	SMC	9.5255	0.0726	6.4780
	GWO-FO-PID	8.2319	0.0179	5.4620

Conclusion

Both the GWO-FO-PID controller and the SMC controller are presented in this study. The authors used MATLAB to develop and execute these approaches, which were then tested on linked micro grid systems with one area and two areas subjected to different disturbances. This study compares the GWO-FO-PID controller's performance to that of the SMC controller and finds that the former performs better generally.

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